

Ailey and curating screen dance into festivals

This capacity building event spoke to some of the following questions:

- The lack of dance films in film festivals – is there a need for curating more dance-related content?
- The lack of diversity in the Cultural Heritage sector - Black and African Diaspora dance community is under-represented: how can we challenge this reality?
- How might we use dance films and curatorial techniques to open up spaces to explore intersectionality through dance?

Each guest speaker had experience of curating and organising a screening of the film AILEY (2021, directed by Jamila Wignot) and brought a unique perspective to the conversation.

Key takeaways:

- The potential of dance to examine difficult questions about racial justice
- The power of film as an ethical medium, extending audiences and extending debate on films and creating 'transformative spaces' through festivals
- The value of curating cross-arts work and bringing people together to create those 'transformative spaces'
- The need to establish ethical practices when working with constituent communities, being 'community connectors', the recognition that working with communities requires time and trust
- The value of using curatorial techniques to create space, connect, open up conversations and discussion on aspects of social justice and intersectionality through the lens of dance heritage.

Video: <https://youtu.be/Ktj5gBqA8Yo>